

Dibromamine-T as an Analytical Reagent : Estimation of Thiosemicarbazide and its Metal Complexes

B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA

Department of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, University of Mysore,
Manasa Gangotri, Mysore-570 006, India.

Manuscript received 30 September 1977, accepted 1 February 1978

A simple, rapid and accurate method for the estimation of thiosemicarbazide and its metal complexes with Zn, Cd, Hg, Co, Ni and Pd in aqueous or pH 4 buffer medium by a direct titration with dibromamine-T (DBT) in presence of sodium acetate and KBr has been developed. A back titration procedure in which TSC and its complexes (including those of Pt) in aqueous or pH 4 buffer medium are oxidised by DBT has also been described. The oxidation involves a twelve electron stoichiometry per TSC molecule in both direct and back titration procedures. The proposed analytical methods are useful for a rapid estimation of TSC and its complexes on a macroscale and also for computing the number of ligand molecules in a TSC metal complex.

THE number of suitable oxidants available in non-aqueous redox titrimetry are limited. Nair *et al* have introduced the organic haloamines, dichloramine-T (DCT)¹ and dibromamine-T (DBT)² as redox titrants in non-aqueous media. The former has been extensively used in our laboratories,^{3,4} to determine a variety of reductants. Recently, Nair and Indrasenan⁵ have employed DBT to determine Sb(III), As(III), Tl(I), Fe(II) and compounds such as ferrocyanide, iodide, ascorbic acid, hydroquinone, hydrazine, aniline, phenol and oxine. The present studies extend their investigations of DBT for estimating thiosemicarbazide and its metal complexes. Thiosemicarbazide (TSC) and its derivatives are well known metal complexing agents. They have a number of applications such as in characterization of aldehydes, ketones and polysaccharides. They are antitubercular, active against influenza, protozoa, smallpox and certain kinds of tumour and are possible pesticides and fungicides, due to their ability to chelate trace metals. The methods for the estimation of TSC reported so far are based on its oxidation by alkali metal hypohalites,^{5,6} chloramine-T,^{4,7} dichloramine-T⁴ and lead tetraacetate.⁸ We have now critically examined the behaviour of DBT towards TSC and its metal complexes. It was found that TSC in the pure state as well as in its complexes is oxidized by DBT with a twelve electron change per molecule under specified conditions. After careful investigations, rapid and accurate analytical techniques have been proposed for estimating TSC and its complexes with zinc group of metals and cobalt, nickel, platinum and palladium, by DBT. The proposed volumetric methods for their estimation include (i) a direct titration between the reductants and DBT in presence of KBr and sodium acetate, with a visual or potentiometric end point and (ii) a back titration procedure in presence of sodium acetate.

Materials and Methods

E. Merck thiosemicarbazide was purified by recrystallisation from aqueous solution. PdCl₂ and H₂PtCl₆.

× H₂O (Johnson-Matthey Ltd., London) were used for preparing the Pt(II) and Pd(II) complexes. The following TSC(L) complexes were prepared by methods reported by us elsewhere : ⁸⁻¹⁰ ML₂X₂, where M = Zn, Cd, Ni or Hg ; X = Cl, NO₃, ClO₄ or $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄ ; CoL₂(NO₃)₂; cis and trans PtL₂Cl₂, PtL₂X₂ where X = Br, I, CN, CNS or NO₃; cis and trans PdL₂(NO₃)₂; PdL₂X₂ where X = Cl, Br, I or CNS ; Neutral complexes M(L-H)₂ where M = Ni, Pt or Pd. Solution of TSC and its complexes were prepared in aqueous medium or in pH 4 acetate buffer (~2 mg/ml). Approximately INKBr 20% sodium acetate, and 10% zinc sulphate solutions were prepared. Triply distilled water was used for preparing the solutions. DBT was prepared and purified by the method of Nair and Indrasenan⁵. An approximately decinormal solution in glacial acetic acid was prepared, standardised by the iodometric method and stored in amber coloured bottles. All other materials and reagents were of accepted grades of purity. A Bajaj potentiometer with a platinum indicator electrode and a reference calomel electrode was used for potentiometric titrations.

1. Direct titration :

(a) *With visual end point* : A direct titration of TSC and its complexes (with the exception of those of Pt) with DBT was found practicable in the presence of sodium acetate and KBr, the former to accelerate the decomposition of DBT and the latter to serve as an indicator to detect the end point in an Andrews type of titration, employing carbon tetrachloride. The presence of a small quantity of ZnSO₄ solution was necessary in the titration of pure TSC with DBT.

Recommended procedure ; Take aliquots of TSC or its complex (~2-60 mg) in a 100 ml iodine flask. Add 5 ml of sodium acetate and 5 ml of KBr and 1 ml of CCl₄ (5 ml of ZnSO₄ solution in case of pure TSC) and titrate with DBT with shaking till the appearance of a faint yellow colour in CCl₄ layer (Appearance of

faint yellow colour in the aqueous layer indicates the approach of end point in the absence of CCl_4). Blank correction was found to be about 0.05 ml of 0.1N DBT. The amount (x mg) of TSC or its complex in the sample solution is given by $x = \frac{M}{E} NV$, where N is the normality of DBT, V, the volume of DBT required, M is the molecular weight of TSC or its complex and E is the number of electrons changing per molecule of TSC or its complex.

(b) *Potentiometric end point* : A potentiometric titration of TSC and its complexes with DBT was possible in presence of sodium acetate (5 ml) and KBr (5 ml). A large potential jump of ~200 – 400 mV was noticed for the addition of 0.1 ml of 0.1N oxidant at the equivalence point. In the absence of sodium acetate, premature end points were obtained. Addition of a small quantity of ZnSO_4 (5 ml) was essential in the titration of pure TSC with DBT.

Platinum complexes of TSC could not be titrated directly with DBT, since their oxidation was non-stoichiometric under these conditions.

2. *Back titration method* :

Preliminary investigations : In preliminary investigations known quantities of TSC or its complex solution were added to a known excessive volume of DBT in an iodine flask. The reaction mixture was set aside for various intervals of time at room temperature with occasional shaking. The excess of DBT left unconsumed was iodometrically determined by back titration with standard sodium thiosulphate.

It was found that with a 40 – 50% excess of DBT, the oxidation of TSC was completed in 20 minutes, if an over-all water content of about 10 – 20% was maintained in the reaction mixture. Stoichiometric oxidation of complexes of Zn, Cd, Hg, Ni and Co took

TABLE 1 – ESTIMATION OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES WITH DIBROMAMINE-T (DIRECT TITRATION)

Compound	Range studied (mg)				
	Taken	Visual end point		Potentiometric end point	
		Found	Deviation %	Found	Deviation %
TSC(L)	2.07-62.10	2.08-61.73	0.10-0.60	2.08-61.75	0.10-0.56
ZnL_2SO_4	2.11-52.77	2.12-52.70	0.10-0.47	2.12-52.70	0.13-0.52
ZnL_2Cl_2	2.09-52.35	2.09-52.27	0.00-0.41	2.09-52.09	0.00-0.41
$\text{ZnL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.05-51.15	2.04-51.27	0.23-0.59	2.04-51.27	0.23-0.59
$\text{ZnL}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$	2.08-52.08	2.09-51.80	0.27-0.54	2.07-51.80	0.10-0.54
CdL_2SO_4	2.03-50.62	2.03-50.50	0.00-0.42	2.03-50.60	0.00-0.44
CdL_2Cl_2	2.06-51.50	2.07-51.30	0.10-0.51	2.05-51.36	0.10-0.49
HgL_2Cl_2	2.03-50.69	2.04-50.61	0.02-0.49	2.04-50.61	0.13-0.49
PdL_2Cl_2	1.34-33.59	1.34-33.47	0.00-0.60	1.35-33.47	0.11-0.75
PdL_2Br_2	1.70-29.74	1.69-29.68	0.00-0.59	1.70-29.68	0.00-0.52
PdL_2I_2	2.40-30.00	2.41-30.06	0.20-0.50	2.41-30.06	0.00-0.50
$\text{PdL}_2(\text{CNS})_2$	1.36-30.51	1.37-30.56	0.16-0.74	1.37-30.36	0.25-0.74
<i>cis</i> - $\text{PdL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	1.32-39.47	1.32-39.40	0.00-0.66	1.31-39.40	0.18-0.76
<i>trans</i> - $\text{PdL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.64-39.59	2.64-39.66	0.00-0.48	2.63-39.66	0.08-0.76
$\text{Pd}(\text{L-H})_2$	1.79-44.79	1.80-44.60	0.11-0.56	1.79-44.85	0.00-0.48
$\text{CoL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.30-57.39	2.30-57.16	0.00-0.44	2.31-57.16	0.26-0.68
$\text{NiL}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.11-52.88	2.12-52.61	0.19-0.52	2.10-52.63	0.09-0.47
$\text{NiL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.11-52.79	2.11-52.57	0.00-0.54	2.10-52.73	0.00-0.51
NiL_2Cl_2	1.88-56.28	1.87-56.19	0.16-0.53	1.89-56.11	0.09-0.53
$\text{Ni}(\text{L-H})_2$	2.04-50.90	2.05-50.66	0.03-0.49	2.04-50.84	0.00-0.59

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES WITH DIBROMAMINE-T (BACK TITRATION)

Compound	Taken	Range studied (mg) Found	% Deviation
TSC(L)	2.07-62.10	2.08-61.75	0.10-0.56
ZnL ₂ SO ₄	2.11-52.77	2.12-52.70	0.03-0.52
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	2.09-52.35	2.09-52.08	0.00-0.52
ZnL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	4.09-51.15	4.11-51.14	0.00-0.49
ZnL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	2.08-52.08	2.09-52.15	0.13-0.48
CdL ₂ SO ₄	2.03-50.62	2.03-50.74	0.00-0.42
CdL ₂ Cl ₂	2.06-51.50	2.07-51.53	0.06-0.49
HgL ₂ Cl ₂	2.03-50.69	2.02-50.83	0.02-0.49
PdL ₂ Cl ₂	1.34-33.59	1.33-33.47	0.15-0.75
PdL ₂ Br ₂	1.70-29.74	1.71-29.68	0.20-0.71
PdL ₂ I ₂	1.20-30.00	1.20-29.93	0.00-0.50
PdL ₂ (CNS) ₂	1.36-30.51	1.35-30.36	0.13-0.74
<i>cis</i> -PdL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2.63-39.47	2.62-39.40	0.20-0.61
<i>trans</i> -PdL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	1.32-39.59	1.32-39.66	0.00-0.48
Pd(L-H) ₂	1.79-44.79	1.80-44.60	0.11-0.56
CoL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2.30-57.39	2.29-57.09	0.19-0.52
NiL ₂ SO ₄ ·3H ₂ O	2.11-52.88	2.10-52.63	0.09-0.47
NiL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ^{II}	2.11-52.79	2.11-52.68	0.00-0.41
NiL ₂ Cl ₂	1.88-56.28	1.89-56.11	0.00-0.53
Ni(L-H) ₂	2.04-50.90	2.04-50.66	0.00-0.59
<i>cis</i> -PtL ₂ Cl ₂	2.11-52.85	2.12-52.63	0.13-0.61
<i>trans</i> -PtL ₂ Cl ₂	1.06-31.86	1.06-31.91	0.00-0.56
PtL ₂ Br ₂	1.78-31.15	1.79-31.22	0.09-0.56
PtL ₂ I ₂	2.54-38.10	2.55-37.99	0.16-0.55
PtL ₂ (CN) ₂	1.02-30.65	1.02-30.53	0.00-0.52
PtL ₂ (CNS) ₂	2.21-33.18	2.21-33.13	0.00-0.54
PtL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	1.35-40.46	1.35-40.58	0.00-0.55
Pt(L-H) ₂	2.75-41.34	2.75-41.47	0.00-0.58

place within 5–10 minutes. Pd and Pt complexes could be oxidised within 10–15 and 30–40 minutes respectively. The rate was very slow with TSC solutions in glacial acetic acid.

Recommended procedure : Add aliquots of TSC or its complex solution to a known excessive volume of 0.1N DBT (~40–50% excess) in an iodine flask (5 ml ZnSO₄ solution in the case of pure TSC) maintaining an over-all water content of about 10–20%. Shake the contents and set aside for the duration mentioned

above. Add 10 ml of 20% potassium iodide solution and titrate with 0.1N sodium thiosulphate (V₁). Run a blank with DBT solution (V₂). The amount of TSC or its complex (x mg) in the sample solution is given by $x = \frac{M}{E}N(V_2 - V_1)$, where N is the normality of thiosulphate and E and M have the significance as before.

Results and Discussion

The ligand TSC in the pure state and in its metal complexes is oxidized with a-12 electron change under both direct and back titration procedures. It was noticed that the CN⁻ and CNS⁻ present in PtL₂(CN)₂, PtL₂(CNS)₂ and PdL₂(CNS)₂ are also oxidised by the oxidant under these conditions with a 2 and 8-electron change per ion respectively. Allowance was made for this fact in calculating the amount of complex recovered. With cobalt complex liberation of one equivalent of iodine by Co³⁺ has been excluded, in recovery calculations.

The stoichiometry of oxidation of TSC in the pure state and in its complexes can be represented as follows :

where M=Zn, Ni, Cd, Hg, Pt or Pd and X=Cl, NO₃, ClO₄, Br, I or $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄

where M=Ni, Pt or Pd, R=p-CH₃-C₆H₄SO₂.

Similar equations can be written for PtL₂(CN)₂, PtL₂(CNS)₂, PdL₂(CNS)₂ and CoL₂(NO₃)₂.

Some typical results of analyses are shown in tables 1 and 2. The tables show the range of amounts of TSC and its complexes employed and recovered and the per cent error in the recovery. Each range covers the amounts present in 8–10 different aliquots of the compound, It is seen that the results are accurate with an error of about 0.5%.

Common anions such as SO₄²⁻, PO₄³⁻, NO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻, Cl⁻ and F⁻ do not interfere but I⁻ ion interferes in direct titration and Br⁻ ion in the back titration. N₂H₄ interferes in both the titrations. It was found that presence of water and alkali acetate accelerates the rate of oxidation.

It can be concluded from the above investigations that the proposed analytical techniques are rapid and accurate and are useful for estimating macroquantities of the ligand in the pure state and in its complexes by a proper adjustment of reaction conditions. Also an

approximate computation of the number of ligand molecules present in a TSC complex can be made by these analytical techniques.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B.T.G.) acknowledges financial assistance from the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, in the form of a Research Fellowship.

References

1. T. J. JACOB and C. G. R. NAIR, *Talanta*, 1972, 19, 347.
2. C. G. R. NAIR and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1976, 23, 239.
3. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and N. M. MADE GOWDA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1973, 42, 420 ; 1975, 44, 5 ; *Talanta*, 1975, 22, 771 ; *Talanta*, 1977, 24, 470 ; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 705.
4. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and B. T. GOWDA, *Talanta*, 1976, 23, 601 ; 1977, 24, 325, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 938 ; *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, 44, 306 ; 1976, 45, 161.
5. A. GAFFRE in 'Volmetric Analysis', I. M. KOLTHOFF and R. BELCHER, Interscience, New York, 1957, Vol. 3, p. 386.
6. J. PIJCK, A. CAMPE and A. CLAEYS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belges*, 1964, 73, 898.
7. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and A. S. A. MURTHY, *Talanta*, 1970, 17, 431 ; *Curr. Sci.*, 1972, 41, 100.
8. B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 470.
9. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and A. S. A. MURTHY, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1972, 25, 1565.
10. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, B. T. GOWDA and A. S. A. MURTHY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 985.